

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS

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Annotation: This article explores innovative methodologies for improving the development of oral speech competencies in students. It emphasizes the importance of these skills in academic and professional settings and addresses common challenges faced by students. The proposed solutions include interactive workshops, technology integration, peer evaluation, real-world applications, public speaking clubs, ongoing feedback mechanisms, a multidisciplinary approach, curriculum integration, mentorship programs, and cultural sensitivity.

Keywords: *Oral Communication, Speech Competencies, Student Development, Innovative Methodologies, Technology Integration, Peer Evaluation, Public Speaking Clubs.*

Effective oral communication is a fundamental skill that plays a crucial role in a student's academic and professional success. Developing strong oral speech competencies not only aids in expressing ideas clearly but also fosters confidence and critical thinking. In this article, we will explore the significance of oral speech competencies, identify common challenges faced by students, and propose innovative methodologies to enhance and refine these crucial skills.

Education competence is a multifaceted concept that encompasses the knowledge, skills, and attributes necessary for effective teaching and learning. It goes beyond subject matter expertise to include pedagogical proficiency, communication skills, adaptability, and the ability to create a supportive and inclusive learning environment. Educators with high education competence can tailor their teaching methods to diverse learning styles, employ innovative instructional strategies, and assess student progress effectively.

Oral speech competencies encompass the ability to articulate thoughts coherently, engage an audience, and convey information persuasively. In academic settings and beyond, these skills are indispensable. Whether it be participating in class discussions, presenting research findings, or engaging in job interviews, effective oral communication is a key determinant of success.

Despite the acknowledged importance of oral speech competencies, many students encounter challenges in developing and refining these skills. Some common obstacles include:

- **Lack of Confidence:** Many students struggle with self-confidence when it comes to public speaking. This lack of confidence can hinder their ability to communicate effectively.
- **Limited Exposure:** In traditional classroom settings, students may not have enough opportunities to practice and refine their oral communication skills, leading to a disconnect between theory and practical application.
- **Fear of Judgment:** The fear of being judged by peers or instructors can create anxiety and apprehension, further impeding the development of oral speech competencies.
- **Inadequate Feedback:** Constructive feedback is essential for improvement, but students often receive limited feedback on their oral presentations, leaving them unsure about areas that need enhancement.

Enhancing oral speech competencies is a dynamic process that requires a multifaceted approach. By acknowledging the challenges students face and implementing innovative methodologies, educational institutions can empower students to communicate effectively, fostering not only academic success but also preparing them for the demands of the professional

world. As we embrace these progressive approaches, we pave the way for a future generation of confident, articulate, and successful communicators.

To achieve a comprehensive improvement in oral speech competencies, it is essential to integrate communication skills seamlessly into the curriculum. Rather than treating communication as a separate entity, educators should embed it throughout various subjects. For instance, literature classes can involve interpretative discussions, science classes can incorporate presentation of research findings, and history classes can include debates. This interdisciplinary approach not only reinforces the importance of communication in diverse contexts but also allows students to apply their skills in a range of scenarios. By weaving communication into the fabric of education, we ensure that students perceive it as an integral aspect of their overall learning experience.

Establishing mentorship programs can significantly contribute to the development of oral speech competencies. Pairing students with mentors who excel in communication can provide personalized guidance and support. Mentors can share their own experiences, offer constructive feedback, and help students navigate the challenges of public speaking. This one-on-one interaction creates a safe space for students to address their concerns, receive tailored advice, and build a mentor-student relationship that extends beyond the academic realm. Mentorship not only enhances oral communication skills but also fosters personal growth and development, nurturing a sense of belonging and confidence among students.

Effective oral communication goes beyond language proficiency; it requires an understanding of cultural nuances and inclusivity. Educators should emphasize the importance of cultural sensitivity in communication, encouraging students to consider diverse perspectives and adapt their language and delivery accordingly. In a globalized world, the ability to communicate respectfully and inclusively with individuals from different backgrounds is a crucial skill.

Conclusion. Integrating discussions on cultural diversity and inclusivity within the framework of oral communication courses helps students develop not only the linguistic aspects of communication but also the interpersonal and intercultural competencies necessary for effective communication in a multicultural society. By fostering cultural awareness, educational institutions contribute to the development of well-rounded communicators equipped to thrive in a globalized workforce.

REFERENCES:

1. McCroskey, J. C., & Richmond, V. P. (1987). *Fundamentals of Public Speaking*. Scott, Foresman.
2. Osborn, M., Osborn, S., Osborn, K., & Osborn, T. (2018). *Public Speaking: Finding Your Voice*. Pearson.
3. Kinicki, A. J., & Fugate, M. (2019). *Organizational Behavior: A Practical, Problem-Solving Approach*. McGraw-Hill Education.
4. Sagdullaev, P. (2023). THE INNOVATIONS AND VARIETY OF APPROACHES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Science and innovation*, 2(B4), 142-148.
5. Sagdullayev, P. K. (2020). Raqamli texnologiyalar vositasida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning til kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish. *PEDAGOGIKA*, 5(1), 19-21. Sagdullaev Pulatbek. (2023). IMPROVING THE LANGUAGE COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS BY MEANS OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES. *Academia Science Repository*, 4(04), 116–124.

6. Sarvinoz, I. (2023). Formation and Development of Artificial Intelligence. Eurasian Journal of Research, Development and Innovation, 21, 14-17.
7. Roebuck, D. B., & LaPointe, L. L. (1990). Communication: The Key to Effective Leadership. Greenwood Publishing Group.